

SURUNKALI BUYRAK KASALLIGIDA YURAK QON-TOMIR ZARARLANISHI PATAFIZIOLOGIYASI.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Surunkali buyrak kasalligi (SBK) bilan kasallangan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfi yuqori bo'lib, koronar arteriya kasalligi, yurak yetishmovchiligi, aritmiya va to'satdan koronar o'lim bilan namoyon bo'ladi. Kardiovaskulyar kasalliklarning tarqalishi SBKning erta bosqichlarida bo'lgan bemorlarda (SBK 1-3 bosqichlari) umumiy aholi bilan solishtirganda sezilarli darajada yuqori bo'lsada, SBKning rivojlangan bosqichlari (4-5 bosqichlari) bo'lgan bemorlarda xavf sezilarli darajada yuqori. SBKning oxirgi bosqichi buyrak kasalligidan ko'ra yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari ushbu yuqori xavf guruhidagi o'limning asosiy sababidir. SBK tizimli va surunkali yallig'lanish jarayonini keltirib chiqaradi, bu esa qon tomirlarni va miokardni qayta qurish jarayonlariga sabab bo'ladi. Bu jarayonlar natijasida qon tomirlarining kalsifikatsiyasi va aterosklerotik shikastlanishi, shuningdek, miokard fibrozi va yurak klapanlarining kalsifikatsiyasiga olib keladi. Shu sababdan, SBK yurak-qon tomir tizimining tez zaiflashishiga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aritmiyalar, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, yurak yetishmovchiligi, surunkali buyrak kasalligi, gemodializ.

ANNOTATION

Patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) are at increased risk of cardiovascular disease, manifested by coronary artery disease, heart failure, arrhythmias, and sudden coronary death. Although the prevalence of cardiovascular disease is significantly higher in patients with early stages of CKD (CKD stages 1-3) compared to the general population, the risk is significantly higher in patients with advanced CKD stages (CKD stages 4-5). Cardiovascular disease rather than kidney disease is the leading cause of death in this high-

risk group. CKD causes a systemic and chronic inflammatory process, which causes remodeling processes of blood vessels and myocardium. As a result of these processes, it leads to calcification of blood vessels and atherosclerotic damage, as well as myocardial fibrosis and calcification of heart valves. For this reason, CKD leads to rapid weakening of the cardiovascular system.

Key words: arrhythmias, cardiovascular diseases, heart failure, chronic kidney disease, hemodialysis.

EPIDEMIOLOGIYASI VA PROGNOZ.

SBK sog'liqni saqlash tizimining global muammosi sifatida tobora rivojlanib bormoqda. Bu jamiyatga va sog'liqni saqlash tizimlariga katta tibbiy va moliyaviy zarar beradi (1). Butun dunyo bo'ylab SBK tarqalishining o'sishi buyrak transplantatsiyasini talab qiladigan oxirgi bosqichga o'tadigan bemorlar sonining ko'payishi bilan birga keladi (2). Hozirgi vaqtda butun dunyo bo'ylab buyrak transplantatsiyasini o'tkazgan 10 million bemordan 3 millionga yaqin bemor SBK 5-bosqichidagi bemorlar hisoblanadi. Bu sonlar 2030-yilgacha 50% dan 100% gacha o'sishi kutilmoqda (3,4). SBK bilan kasallanish va tarqalishining ortib borishi sabablariga aholining yoshi, 2-tip qandli diabet va gipertenziya tarqalishining ortishi (5) va SBKning dastlabki bosqichlarida aniqlash darajasi pastligi kiradi (6,7).

SBK ta'rifi va tasnifi Milliy Buyrak Jamg'armasi tomonidan 2002-yilda (8) va 2004-yilda Buyrak kasalligining global natijalarini yaxshilash bo'yicha tuzilgan xalqaro guruh tomonidan kiritilgan (9). Buyrak shikastlanishini klinik baholash paytida kuzatilgan o'zgarishlar buyrak funksiyasi pasayganligini ko'rsatadi (9,10). Surunkali buyrak kasalligi buyrak shikastlanishi yoki koptokchalar filtratsiya tezligi $<60 \text{ ml/min/1,73 m}^2$ ko'rinishida bo'ladi, ular 3 oydan ko'p muddat davomida saqlanadi va klinik belgilar bilan namoyon bo'ladi (8,11). Ko'pgina buyrak kasalliklarida buyrak shikastlanishi albumin-kreatinin nisbati $> 30 \text{ mg / g}$ sifatidagi albuminuriya mavjudligi bilan aniqlanishi mumkin (1-rasm). Surunkali buyrak kasalligi bo'lgan populyatsiyada albuminuriya va kardiorenal xavf o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni ko'rsatadigan dalillar ko'p (13,14). Albuminuriya yurak-qon tomir yoki buyrak xavfi uchun yoki ikkalasining rivojlanishining prognostik belgisi hisoblanadi

(15). Albuminuriyaning yuqori darajalari KFTdan mustaqil ravishda o'lim xavfining bosqichma-bosqich o'sishini ko'rsatadi (12,16).

Britaniyalik shifokor Richard Bright birinchi bo'lib surunkali buyrak kasalligi yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan bog'liqligi haqida ma'lumot bergan (17). SBK bilan kasallangan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari uchun aniq xavf mavjud. SBK bilan kasallangan 4-va 5-bosqichdagi barcha bemorlarning 50 foizida yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bor (18), va yurak-qon tomir asoratlardan o'lim rivojlangan. SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda barcha o'limlarning 40% dan 50% gacha 4-bosqichda shuningdek, buyrak kasalligining oxirgi bosqichida 26% ga teng (19,20). Miokard infarkti va insult kabi o'limga olib keladigan ateroskleroz bilan bog'liq bo'lgan asoratlarning yuqori xavfi bilan bir qatorda, yurak-qon tomir yetishmovchiligi va o'limga olib keladigan aritmiyalar, ayniqsa SBKning rivojlangan bosqichlarida yuzaga keladi. 70 dan ortiq dializ qabul qilmaydigan SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarda gipertenziya, qandli diabet va dislipidemiya kabi klassik yurak-qon tomir xavf omillarini davolash SBKning yurak-qon tomir xavfiga ta'sirini kamaytirmadi (21). SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini rivojlanish xavfi buyrak kasalligining oxirgi bosqichida oshib ketadi va shuning uchun SBKga yurak qon-tomir kasalliklari rivojlanishi uchun eng kuchli xavf omillaridan biri sifatida qaraladi (22).

PATAFIZIOLOGIYASI

SBKda yurak qon-tomir asoratlari rivojlanishiga 2 ta asosiy mexanizm sabab bo'ladi. Bir tomondan, buyraklar shikastlanishi yoki buyrak yetishmovchiligiga javoban gormonlar, fermentlar va sitokinlarni chiqarilishi, bu esa qon tomirlarida o'zgarishlarga olib keladi (23). Boshqa tomondan, gemodinamik o'zgarishlar yurak shikastlanishiga sabab bo'ladi (24). An'anaviy yurak-qon tomir xavf omillari SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda juda keng tarqalgan va ularning aterosklerotik qon tomir kasalliklariga qo'shgan hissasi, ayniqsa, SBKning dastlabki bosqichlarida muhim ahamiyatga ega (25). Gipertoniya, qandli diabet, dislipidemiya va chekish nafaqat aterosklerotik yurak-qon tomir va serebrovaskulyar oqibatlariga balki SBK rivojlanishiga ham hissa qo'shadi (26).

Gipertenziya SBKning o'ziga xos belgisidir. Natriyning ushlanib qolishi, nefronlar sonining kamayishi va renin-angiotenzin-aldosteron tizimining faollashishi bilan bog'liq

bo'lgan hajmning kengayishi turli xil antigipertenziv mexanizmlarni ishga tushiradi va immun-yallig'lanish tizimini faollashtiradi. SBKda natriy mushaklar va terida suv tutilishsiz to'planadi, bu esa buyraklar faoliyatining buzilishi darajasi bilan bog'liq (27). Hajmning ortishi ikkilamchi bo'lib, SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda endogen kardiotonik steroidlar ishlab chiqarilishi ortadi. Ushbu steroid birikmalarining yuqori darajalari vazodilatatsion mexanizmlarni buzishi orqali qon bosimini oshiradi (28). Yallig'lanish bilan bog'liq bo'lgan qon tomirlarining qattiqlashishi, giperfosfatemiya va ikkilamchi giperparatiroidizm tufayli qon tomirlarining kalsifikatsiyasi sistolik qon bosimining oshishiga asosiy sabab bo'ladi (24). Asimmetrik dimetil arginin va endotelial disfunktsiya va azot oksidi sintazasining endogen ingibitorlarining to'planishi tufayli azot oksidi ishlab chiqarilishining buzilishi SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda buyrak funksiyasining pasayishiga parallel. Ushbu moddalarning progressiv to'planishi va endotelin darajasining parallel ravishda ko'tarilishi gipertenziyaga olib keladi (29).

Giperglikemiya ham SBK rivojlanishi bilan bog'liqdir. Iqtisodiy jihatdan rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda semizlik va 2-tip qandli diabet ham SBK uchun asosiy xavf omillari hisoblanadi (30). Giperglikemiya turli mexanizmlar orqali mikro va makrovaskulyar asoratlarni keltirib chiqaradi, shu jumladan glikosidlanishning kuchayishi, reaktiv kislorod turlarining hujayra ichidagi hosil bo'lishi va asosan epigenetik o'zgarishlar orqali yallig'lanishga qarshi yo'llarni faollashtiradigan va qo'llab-quvvatlaydigan glikozillangan oqsillarni to'plash (31). Yallig'lanishga qarshi leptin, rezistin, o'simta nekrozi omili, interleykin 1beta (IL1b) va interleykin 6 (IL6) va yallig'lanishga qarshi adipokin, interleykin 10 sintezidagi nomutanosiblik bunga sabab bo'ladi. Sitokinlar SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda QD va buyrak shikastlanishi bilan bog'liq (32). Yallig'lanish mediatorlari qandli diabet va SBK uchun dolzarbdir (30).

Dislipidemiya SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda yuqori zichlikdagi lipoprotein (YZLP), past zichlikdagi lipoprotein (PZLP) o'zgaruvchan darajalari bilan tavsiflanadi. Triglitseridlarga boy bo'lgan PZLP va JPZLP metabolizmi SBKda o'zgaradi. Bundan tashqari, bu holatda xolesterinni teskari tashish YZLP vositachiligidagi jarayon buziladi. YZLP ham, PZLP ham SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda o'zgaradi, bu ularning aterogen faoliyatini oshiradi (33). Jigar triglitseridlarga boy PZLPni hosil qiladi. Triglitseridlar

lipoprotein lipaza (LPL) tomonidan gidrolizlanadi va JPZLP va O'ZLP zarralarini va nihoyat PZLP zarralarini hosil qilish uchun kamayadi. PZLP zarralari xolesterinni jigar va periferik to'qimalarga olib boradi. Triglitseridlarga boy xilomikronlar lipidlarni ichakdan jigarga tashiydi. Xilomikronlarning PZLP tomonidan gidrolizlanishi erkin yog ' kislotalarini hosil qiladi va bu jarayonda xilomikronlar kamayadi oxir-oqibat PZLP retseptorlari orqali jigar tomonidan ushlanadi. YZLP zarralari xolesterinning teskari transportini boshqarish uchun asosiy hisoblanadi (33).

Tomirlarning silliq mushak hujayralari qon tomirlarining medial qavatining tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, ular SBKda kuzatilgan gemodinamik o'zgarishlar tufayli kontraktil fenotipdan sintetik fenotipga o'tishlari mumkin (34). Natijada paydo bo'lgan yurak-qon tomir kalsifikatsiyasi SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda sezilarli darajada tezlashadi. SBKga qo'shimcha ravishda, qandli diabet kalsifikatsiyaning rivojlanishini yanada kuchaytiradi. Markaziy arterial tomirlarning kalsifikatsiyasi puls to'lqinining tezligini oshirishga, puls to'lqinining erta aks etishiga, yurakka keyingi yuklamaning oshishiga va yurak yetishmovchiligiga sabab bo'ladi (35). Gemodinamik o'zgarishlar koronar perfuziyaning pasayishi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan chap qorincha gipertrofiyasini keltirib chiqaradi. Tomirlarning kalsifikatsiyasining ayniqsa og'ir shakli uremik kalsifik arteriolopatiya bo'lib, u gipodermik arteriolalarga kalsiyning cho'kishi natijasida teri nekroziga olib keladi va o'lim darajasi yuqori (36).

SBKda miokarddagi o'zgarishlar

SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda patologik miokard fibroziga xarakterli o'zgarishlar kuzatiladi, kapillyarlar va kardiomyositlar o'rtasida kollagen cho'kishi va yurak gipertrofiyasi uremik kardiomyopatiyaning belgilaridir (37). Chap qorincha gipertrofiyasi (CHQG) SBK bilan og'rigan barcha bemorlarning taxminan uchdan birida mavjud bo'lib, buyrak yetishmovchiligining so'nggi bosqichida bo'lgan bemorlarda 70% dan 80% gacha ko'tariladi. SBKda CHQGga uchta asosiy mexanizm sabab bo'ladi: 1- yuklamadan keyingi va 2- yuklamadan oldingi omillar, shuningdek 3- keyingi va oldingi yuklanish bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan omillar (38). Keyingi yuklama bilan bog'liq omillarga anormal arterial qattqlik, tizimli arterial qarshilik kuchayishi va sistolik gipertenziya kiradi, bu esa dastlabki konsentrik CHQGga olib keladi (39). Chap qorinchaning uzluksiz haddan tashqari

yuklanishi keyinchalik noto'g'ri o'zgarishlarga va kardiomiotsitlarning o'limiga olib keladi, bu esa o'z navbatida eksantrik gipertrofiyaga va keyinchalik chap qorincha kengayishiga, sistolik disfunktsiyaga va qisqarish fraktsiyasining pasayishiga olib keladi(38). SBKda CHQG patofiziologiyasidagi oldindan yuklanish bilan bog'liq omillar tomir ichidagi hajmning kengayishini o'z ichiga oladi, bu esa hajmning haddan tashqari yuklanishiga, miokard hujayralari uzunligining oshishiga va chap qorincha eksantrik yoki assimetrik qayta tuzilishiga olib keladi (37). Oldingi va keying yuklama bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan omillar hujayra ichidagi mediatorlar va progressiv CHQGga hissa qo'shadigan yo'llarni o'z ichiga oladi (39). Uremik kardiomiopatiyaning CHQGdan tashqari ikkinchi o'ziga xos belgisi CHQGning o'zidan mustaqil ravishda yuzaga keladigan miokard fibrozining rivojlanishidir (37). SBK bilan og'rigan bemorlarda yurak fibrozi kapillyarlar va kardiomiotsitlar o'rtasida diffuz kollagen cho'kishi bilan xarakterlanadi, bu esa keyinchalik yurakning kengayishiga olib keladigan noto'g'ri qorincha gipertrofiyasiga o'tadi (39).

XULOSA

SBK bilan kasallangan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfi yuqori, yurak-qon tomir asoratlari o'limning asosiy sababidir. SBKda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytirish uchun bir nechta yangi davolash usullari klinik ishlab chiqilmoqda. So'nggi yigirma yil ichida og'ir buyrak yetishmovchiligi bo'lgan va dializ bilan davolanayotgan bemorlarning yomon prognozini kamaytirish tibbiyotning eng muhim muammosi sifatida paydo bo'ldi. Ushbu bemorlarda yurak qon-tomir asoratlari bo'yicha tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish sog'liqni saqlashning ustuvor yo'nalishi hisoblanadi.

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